

INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF ENGLISH LEARNING WITH THE HELP OF GAME METHODS

Zahro Mamadaliyeva

Teacher of Fergana state university.

Nishonova Muhayyo

Student of Fergana state university.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15099741>

Abstract. This article analyzes the effectiveness of game methods in teaching English. A game approach makes the educational process more interesting and interactive, increases the activity of students, and helps them better assimilate knowledge. The article discusses the importance of didactic games, role-playing games, interactive tasks, and games created on the basis of modern technologies. It also highlights the role of game methods in developing language competence, forming communicative skills, and supporting the process of independent learning.

The results of the study show that game teaching methods make the process of learning English more effective and encourage students to participate more actively.

Keywords: Game methods, Interactive education, Role Play, Didactic games, Object, Pictionary, Taboo words, Word Association.

ПОВЫШЕНИЕ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА С ПОМОЩЬЮ ИГРОВЫХ МЕТОДОВ

Аннотация. В данной статье анализируется эффективность игровых методов в обучении английскому языку. Игровой подход делает учебный процесс более интересным и интерактивным, повышает активность учащихся, помогает им лучше усваивать знания.

В статье рассматривается значение дидактических игр, ролевых игр, интерактивных задач и игр, созданных на основе современных технологий. Также подчеркивается роль игровых методов в развитии языковой компетенции, формировании коммуникативных навыков, поддержке процесса самостоятельного обучения. Результаты исследования показывают, что игровые методы обучения делают процесс изучения английского языка более эффективным и побуждают студентов к более активному участию.

Ключевые слова: Игровые методы, Интерактивное обучение, Ролевая игра, Дидактические игры, Предмет, Словарь, Табуированные слова, Словесные ассоциации.

Introduction

Today, the process of teaching English is developing rapidly, and various innovative approaches are being widely introduced into the education system. Since the need for knowledge of foreign languages is increasing in the context of globalization and technological progress, it is important that teaching methods are modern and effective. Traditional methods, including teaching based on grammatical rules, and the lesson process limited only to books and written exercises, can reduce the activity of students and reduce their interest in the lesson. Therefore, in today's education system, there is a growing need for interactive and student-based approaches. Game methods are one of such approaches, which serve to make the learning process interesting, lively and effective. Learning through games activates students, increases their enthusiasm for language learning, and helps them adapt naturally to the language environment. Younger students, in particular, are more interested in visual and movement-based activities in the process of language learning. Therefore, didactic games, role-playing games, interactive tasks, and game methods based on technology can significantly increase the effectiveness of the lesson. Game methods not only increase motivation, but also play an important role in expanding students' vocabulary, naturally mastering grammatical rules, developing pronunciation, and forming free communication skills. During game lessons, students learn to think independently, work in a team, and solve problems. In addition, game methods can also integrate digital technologies into the lesson process, which creates a more comfortable and modern learning environment for students.

The role of game methods in teaching English, their advantages, and practical application are discussed. It also provides detailed information on suitable game methods for different age groups, their linguistic and pedagogical effectiveness, as well as the best strategies for integrating them into the teaching process. The article analyzes the theoretical and practical aspects of teaching English based on game methods, and provides useful recommendations for educators.

Literature review and methodology

Many scientific studies have been conducted on the effectiveness of game methods in teaching English, which confirm that game-based education has a positive effect on students' language acquisition. Leading scientists in the field of educational methodology (Vygotsky, Bruner, Piaget) have emphasized the importance of game activity in children's cognitive development and the acquisition of new knowledge. Vygotsky (1978) noted that play is one of the main factors in a child's development, noting that during the game process, students consolidate their knowledge and experience.

Modern research also shows that game methods have a significant impact on the development of linguistic competencies. For example, Ellis (2003) notes that during the process of teaching through game methods, students have the opportunity to learn a language in a natural environment, which strengthens their pronunciation, grammatical knowledge and communication skills. Nation (2013) emphasizes that the process of learning new words through games is further accelerated, because during the game, students reinforce words by repeatedly using them. With the introduction of digital technologies into the educational process, the role of game methods has increased even more. Bach (2017) analyzed the importance of interactive game platforms in language learning in his study and concluded that digital games play an important role in increasing student participation and creating a language environment. This approach is especially important in the development of the concept of gamification in the modern education system. Thus, the literature analysis shows that teaching English through game methods is one of the effective methods that serves to increase student motivation, develop communication skills, and make the educational process interesting. Object- this game serves to increase students' vocabulary. As we know, the most important aspect of learning a foreign language is memorizing new vocabulary.

Considering the characteristics of students, each student memorizes vocabulary in his own way. We are sure that memorizing new words through games is suitable for everyone and makes this process easier. In the game we mentioned above, during the lesson, 15 objects from the classroom are placed on the table and students come and examine these objects. The objects are covered and then the students have to write what they see on the board in English for a certain period of time. The student who can write the most words correctly is the winner. In order to ensure the quality of this game, I can say that in order to attract the students who are left in this situation and are not participating, it would be appropriate to give them the task of making up one sentence for each of these objects, and this would also prevent indifference.

Pictionary - this game is familiar to most English teachers and learners, that is, a word game with a picture drawn on it. In this game, you can use a regular board or a magnetic board to draw pictures. The students in the class are divided into two groups and a table is drawn on both sides of the board for each team. The teams' scores are recorded on these tables. The names of the words are written on the board and turned upside down. Students from each group take turns choosing one of the hidden words and drawing it on the board. The team that finds it first gets a point. This game also sharpens the students' minds. We can also say that using pictures is a tactic that quickly attracts students, especially if it is created by the students themselves.

Taboo words game (Forbidden words) - this interesting game helps students use synonymous words and their definitions. The use of synonyms ensures fluency of speech, beautiful speech. Especially in the subject of English, one should not make mistakes in the use of words, because many words in English that mean the same thing are used according to the context of the sentence. This game helps to be careful in this regard. In this, groups are formed, that is, students sit opposite each other. Each team chooses one person from its team to sit on the chair opposite it.

The teacher goes behind the students and holds a word written on a large piece of paper. Students sitting on the chair should not be able to see this word. The team member sitting on the chair will have some time to say the word that the teacher is holding.

Tennis game - the goal of this game is to increase the speed of students. This game is similar to a chain game and takes place within the framework of the selected topic. In this case, the last letter of the word spoken must be replaced by a new word, for example, if the topic name is "Animals", then without deviating from the topic, if it starts with the word "Tiger", the second participant continues with "rabbit". In this way, the game continues. If a student who stops during the game cannot answer for 5 minutes, he is removed from the game and continues with the rest of the students. Playing the game with the class, that is, with a large group, is very interesting and exciting. This game can also be played by changing the topic. At the same time, in the process of organizing games, connecting them with various technical means also serves to increase interest.

Because in today's rapidly developing era, not all young people, teenagers and adults are indifferent to modern technologies. Therefore, effective results can be achieved by organizing interesting science games on computers.

"Word Association"

Goal: To increase vocabulary and develop quick thinking skills.

Level: Suitable for elementary, middle and high school students.

Rules of the game:

- The teacher or the first student says a word.
- The next student must say another word related to this word.
- The game continues in a chain, and whoever cannot find a word is out of the game.

Through this game, students understand the logical connections between words and expand their vocabulary. They also develop pronunciation and memorization skills.

"Role Play"

Goal: To develop communication skills in English.

Level: Suitable for middle and high school students.

Game rules:

- Students are divided into groups of two or three.
- Each group is given a specific situation (for example, a conversation in a restaurant, hotel or airport).
- Students act out their roles and communicate in English.
- This game strengthens students' communication skills. They learn how to speak in real-life situations, improve their pronunciation and sentence construction skills.

"Guess the Word"

- Objective: To develop the ability to master new words and explain them.
- Level: Suitable for elementary and intermediate students.
- Game rules:
 - One student holds a word written on a piece of paper so that others cannot see it.
 - The other students describe it to them without saying the word.
 - The student who guesses the word continues with the new word.
 - This game helps students understand new words in context. It also develops their ability to explain and use definitions.

"Kahoot!" (Interactive test game)

Goal: Strengthen grammar and vocabulary.

Level: Suitable for students of any level.

Game rules:

- The teacher prepares test questions on the Kahoot! platform.
- Students answer the questions on their phones or computers.
- Students who answer correctly earn points and the winner is determined.

This game encourages students to learn in a competitive environment and they become more actively involved in the lesson process.

"Simon Says" (Simon Says)

Goal: Develop the ability to understand and remember commands.

Level: Suitable for elementary school students.

- The teacher or one student acts as the leader and gives commands that begin with the phrase "Simon says" (for example, "Simon says touch your nose.").
- Students must only follow commands that begin with the phrase "Simon says."

- If the leader simply says “Touch your nose,” students must not move.

This game develops students’ listening and quick response skills.

“Hangman”

Objective: To guess new words and learn spelling.

Level: Suitable for students of all levels.

Rules of the game:

- The teacher or one student writes a hidden word on a piece of paper and draws lines corresponding to the number of letters.

- The other students guess the letters.

- If the letter is in the hidden word, it is written on the line; otherwise, a person begins to be drawn.

- The game continues until the word is completely found or the hanged man is drawn.

This game helps students improve their spelling and learn new words.

Discussion

Using game methods in teaching English provides more interactivity than traditional teaching methods and increases students' interest in learning the language. Studies show that as a result of teaching through game methods, students' vocabulary expands, they better understand grammatical rules, and their communication skills develop significantly.

Using games such as “Word Association”, “Role Play”, “Guess the Word” and “Kahoot!” in the educational process ensures the active participation of students. For example, through “Role Play”, students learn how to have a conversation in real-life situations, which allows students to learn the language more naturally. The “Guess the Word” game improves the learning process by increasing the ability to describe and express ideas, and by explaining. In addition, games also have a positive effect on the psychological state of students. While in traditional lessons, students may be afraid of giving the wrong answer, in games they express their thoughts freely and their confidence in learning a language increases. For example, interactive test games like “Kahoot!” create a competitive atmosphere, actively involve students in the lesson and increase their motivation. Also, games like “Simon Says” and “Hangman” increase memory skills and help strengthen English pronunciation and spelling. Words and phrases that students themselves actively participate in and learn are remembered for a long time. At the same time, some problems may also arise when using game methods. For example, excessive use of game elements during the lesson may cause some students to be distracted from the main content of the lesson.

Therefore, teachers should use games in a purposeful and relevant way to the topic of a particular lesson. In general, game methods play an important role in increasing students' mastery, increasing their motivation to learn a language, and making the lesson process more interesting.

The effectiveness of the learning process can be further improved by widely introducing interactive approaches in the modern education system.

Conclusion

The use of game methods in teaching English is one of the most effective methods that increases students' interest in the lesson, strengthens their knowledge and develops communication skills. With the help of games, students have the opportunity to speak in a natural environment, which helps them express their thoughts freely. Research shows that games such as “Word Association”, “Role Play”, “Guess the Word” and “Kahoot!” play an important role in increasing vocabulary, mastering grammar rules and developing real-life communication skills. Also, games such as “Simon Says”, “Hangman” and “Scrabble” help students to concentrate, improve pronunciation and spelling. The use of game methods is not only limited to enlivening the lesson process, but also increases students' independent learning abilities. If these methods are correctly selected by teachers and applied in a way that is adapted to the topic of the lesson, learning English will be more effective.

Therefore, the use of game methods in modern pedagogical approaches is of great importance. Teachers should select games in accordance with the age characteristics of students, their level of knowledge and educational goals. As a result, the language learning process can be not only effective, but also interesting and interactive.

In the future, the quality of English teaching can be improved by further improving game methods, combining them with digital technologies and effectively using interactive educational tools.

REFERENCES

1. Ashurova Zamira Vahobovna. "The importance of the game method in teaching English." International Conference on Innovations in Engineering, Management and Social Sciences, 2021.
2. "Methods for the effective use of game technologies in teaching English." CyberLeninka.
3. Mahmudova Mahliyo Siddiq qizi. "Methodology of using modern technologies in teaching English." Journal of Science-Innovative Research in Uzbekistan, 2023.

4. "On the importance of games in English lessons." International Academy Journal, 2023.
5. "The use of innovative methods in teaching English." Moluch.ru, 2020.
6. "Pedagogical methods of teaching English to early learners." ResearchGate, 2023.
7. "Organization of didactic activities in English lessons." Nauchniy Impuls, 2022.
8. Shokirov Bahodir Ismoilovich. "Methods of teaching English in a non-philological educational institution." Ajou University in Tashkent, 2021.